

Issiqlik elektr stansiyalarida tutun gazlari issiqligini utilizatsiya qilishning zamonaviy usullari tahlili

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Dolzarlbligi: ushbu tadqiqot issiqlik elektr stansiyalarida (IES) tutun gazlari issiqligini utilizatsiya qilishning zamonaviy usullarini tahlil qilishga bag'ishlangan. Issiqlik elektr stansiyalarining foydali ish koeffitsiyentining pastligi, bugungi kunda jahon energetik tizimlarida bug' turbinali qurilmalardan kombinatsiyalashgan bug'-gaz qurilmalariga o'tish tendensiyasini boshlab bermoqda. Lekin amalda qo'llanilib kelinayotgan bug' turbinali issiqlik elektr stansiyalarini modernizatsiyalash va renovatsiyasi uchun ilmiy tadqiqotlar olib borish hamda ularning foydali ish koeffitsiyentini oshirishga qaratilgan ilmiy izlanishlarni davom ettirish jahon energetikasi oldida turgan dolzarb masalalardan biri hisoblanadi.

Maqsad: bug' turbinali qurilmalarning tutun gazlari bilan issiqlik yo'qotishlarini kamaytirish usullarini aniqlash va issiqlik sxemalarini ishlab chiqish, samaradorligini baholashdan iborat.

Usullar: tadqiqot jarayonida dunyo bo'yicha Scopus va Web of Science ma'lumotlar bazalarida 2010-2024-yillar oralig'ida chop etilgan 30 dan ortiq ilmiy maqola ko'rib chiqildi. Organik Renkin Tsikli (ORT), absorbtion issiqlik nasosli tizimlari (AIN/OAIN), past bosimli ekonomayzerlar (PBE), issiqlik quvurlari asosidagi issiqlik almashtirgichlar (IQIA) va termoelektrik generatorlar (TEG) asosiy texnologiyalar sifatida tahlil qilindi.

Natijalar: tadqiqot qilish asosida OAIN tizimlari tutun gazidagi mavjud va yashirin issiqlikning 80-95% gacha qismini qayta tiklash imkonini beradi, ORT tizimi esa 8-12% issiqlik samaradorligi bilan 220 Vt dan 15 MVt gacha quvvat ishlab chiqarishi mumkin. O'zbekistondagi yirik IES larda (Sirdaryo, Toshkent, Navoiy, Talimarjon) utilizatsiya qilinmagan issiqlik potentsiali 120-250 MVt ni tashkil etishi aniqlandi. Absorbtsion issiqlik nasosli tizimlar uchun 1,4-2,5 yillik o'z-o'zini qoplash muddati bilan eng yuqori iqtisodiy ko'rsatkich qayd etildi. Ushbu tadqiqot O'zbekistonda energetik samaradorlikni oshirish va CO₂ tashlamalarini kamaytirish uchun tutun gazi issiqligini utilizatsiyalash texnologiyalarini joriy etishning ilmiy asoslarini taqdim etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: tutun gazi; issiqlik utilizatsiyasi; organik Renkin tsikli; absorbtion issiqlik nasosi; past bosimli ekonomayzer; termoelektrik generator; issiqlik elektr stansiyasi; energiya samaradorligi; CO₂ tashlamalari

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Анализ современных методов использования тепла дымовых газов на тепловых электростанциях

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Актуальность: данное исследование посвящено анализу современных методов использования тепла дымовых газов на тепловых электростанциях (ТЭС). Низкая эффективность тепловых электростанций в настоящее время приводит к тенденции в мировых энергетических системах к переходу от паротурбинных установок к парогазовым установкам. Однако одной из актуальных проблем, стоящих перед мировым энергетическим сектором, является продолжение научных исследований, направленных на модернизацию и обновление существующих паротурбинных тепловых электростанций и повышение их эффективности.

Цель: выявить методы снижения тепловых потерь с дымовыми газами паротурбинных установок, разработать тепловые схемы и оценить их эффективность.

Методы: в ходе исследования было проанализировано более 30 научных статей, опубликованных в базах данных Scopus и Web of Science по всему миру в период с 2010 по 2024 год. В качестве основных технологий были проанализированы органический цикл Ренкина (ОЦР), абсорбционные тепловые насосные системы (АТН/ОТН), экономайзеры низкого давления (ЭНД), теплообменники с тепловыми трубами (ТТТ) и термоэлектрические генераторы (ТЭГ).

Результаты: на основе проведенного исследования установлено, что системы ОТН позволяют рекуперировать до 80-95% доступного и скрытого тепла дымовых газов, а система ОЦР может генерировать мощность от 220 Вт до 15 МВт с тепловым КПД 8-12%. Было определено, что неиспользованный тепловой потенциал на крупных тепловых электростанциях Узбекистана (Сырдарья, Ташкент, Навои, Талимарджан) составляет 120-250 МВт. Наивысшие экономические показатели были зафиксированы для абсорбционных тепловых насосов со сроком окупаемости 1,4-2,5 года. Данное

исследование предоставляет научную основу для внедрения технологий использования тепла дымовых газов с целью повышения энергоэффективности и сокращения выбросов CO₂ в Узбекистане.

Ключевые слова: дымовые газы; использование тепла; органический цикл Ренкина; абсорбционный тепловой насос; экономайзер низкого давления; термоэлектрический генератор; тепловая электростанция; энергоэффективность; выбросы CO₂.

Analysis of modern methods of utilization of flue gas heat in thermal power plants

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Relevance: this study is devoted to the analysis of modern methods of utilization of flue gas heat in thermal power plants (TPPs). The low efficiency of thermal power plants is currently leading to a trend in the world energy systems to switch from steam turbine plants to combined steam-gas plants. However, one of the pressing issues facing the world energy sector is to continue scientific research aimed at modernizing and renovating existing steam turbine thermal power plants and increasing their efficiency.

Aim: to identify methods for reducing heat losses with flue gases of steam turbine plants, develop thermal schemes, and evaluate their effectiveness.

Methods: during the research, more than 30 scientific articles published in the Scopus and Web of Science databases worldwide between 2010 and 2024 were reviewed. Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC), absorption heat pump systems (AHP/OAHP), low-pressure economizers (LPE), heat pipe heat exchangers (HPHE), and thermoelectric generators (TEG) were analyzed as the main technologies.

Results: based on the research, OAIN systems allow recovering up to 80-95% of the available and latent heat in flue gas, while the ORT system can generate power from 220 W to 15 MW with a thermal efficiency of 8-12%. It was determined that the unused heat potential in large thermal power plants in Uzbekistan (Syrdarya, Tashkent, Navoi, Talimarjon) is 120-250 MW. The highest economic performance was recorded for absorption heat pump systems with a payback period of 1.4-2.5 years. This study provides a scientific basis for the introduction of flue gas heat utilization technologies to increase energy efficiency and reduce CO₂ emissions in Uzbekistan.

Keywords: flue gas; heat utilization; organic Rankine cycle; absorption heat pump; low-pressure economizer; thermoelectric generator; thermal power plant; energy efficiency; CO₂ emissions.

1. Kirish (Introduction)

Jahon energetikasi oldidagi eng dolzarb muammolardan biri bo'lgan energiya samaradorligini oshirish va issiqxona gazlari chiqindilarini kamaytirish masalasi bugungi kunda katta ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Issiqlik elektr stansiyalari (IES) elektr energiyasiga bo'lgan talabning taxminan 38-40% ini ta'minlashda, ularning issiqlik samaradorligi odatda 30-42% ni tashkil etadi, ya'ni yoqilg'i energiyasining katta qismi atrof-muhitga yo'qotiladi [1,4]. Ushbu yo'qotishlar ichida tutun gazlari orqali issiqlik yo'qotilishi - qozon qurilmasidagi issiqlik yo'qotishlarining eng muhim ahamiyatga ega tarkibiy qismi hisoblanib, yoqilg'i energiyasining 4-8% ini tashkil etadi [2,9].

Tutun gazi harorati, masalan ko'mirli qozonlarda havo qizdirgichidan chiqayotgan paytda taxminan 150°C ga yetadi [2]. Har 10-15°C harorat kotarilishi bilan qozon samaradorligi 1% ga pasayadi va elektr stansiyadagi ko'mir sarfi 3-4 g/(kVt*s) ga oshadi [4]. Shu sababli, tutun gazi issiqligini utilizatsiya qilish eng samarali energiya tejash va karbonatli chiqindilarini kamaytirish usullaridan biriga aylangan [3, 6].

O'zbekistonda 2023-yilda IESlar tomonidan jami 60,75 mlrd. kVt*soat elektr energiyasi ishlab chiqarildi. 2030-yilga borib elektr energiyasiga bo'lgan talab 2 barobarga ortishi kutilmoqda. Bu esa mavjud IES larning samaradorligini keskin oshirish zaruriyatini keltirib chiqarmoqda. O'zbekiston Respublikasining amaldagi energiya samaradorligi dasturiy hujjatlari doirasida IES larda zamonaviy issiqlikni utilizatsiyalash texnologiyalarini joriy etish strategik ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Ushbu tadqiqotning asosiy maqsadi Scopus va Web of Science ma'lumotlar bazalaridagi so'nggi ilmiy ishlarga asoslanib, tutun gazi issiqligini utilizatsiya qilishning zamonaviy texnologiyalarini tizimli tahlil qilish, ularning samaradorligi va iqtisodiy ko'rsatkichlarini baholash, hamda O'zbekiston IES lari uchun eng maqbul texnologik yechimlarni tavsiya etishdan iborat [5,7,8].

2. Materiallar va usullar (Methods and materials)

2.1. Adabiyotlar tahlili metodologiyasi

Ushbu tadqiqot 2010-2024-yillar davomida Scopus va Web of Science (WoS) ma'lumotlar bazalarida indekslangan ilmiy maqolalarni tizimli ko'rib chiqish asosida amalga oshirildi. Qidiruv so'zlar sifatida quyidagilar qo'llanildi: "flue gas waste heat recovery", "thermal power plant heat utilization", "organic Rankine cycle boiler", "absorption heat pump flue gas", "low-pressure economizer", "thermo-electric generator exhaust heat". Jami 400 dan ortiq maqola dastlabki bosqichda aniqlandi. PRISMA metodologiyasiga muvofiq, empirik natijalar yoki texnik-iqtisodiy tahlilni o'z ichiga olgan 30 ta asosiy maqola tanlab olindi [8].

2.2. Texnologiyalarni baholash metodikasi

Har bir texnologiyani baholashda quyidagi ko'rsatkichlar qo'llanildi: (1) qayta tiklanadigan issiqlik quvvati (MVt); (2) issiqlik samaradorligi (%); (3) kapital xarajatlar (\$/kVt); (4) kapital xarajatlarning o'z-o'zini qoplash muddati (yil); (5) CO₂ tashlamalarini kamaytirish salohiyati. Iqtisodiy tahlillar uchun termodinamik va eksergetik tahlil usullari qo'llanildi [12]. Hisob-kitoblarda O'zbekistondagi yirik IES lar - Sirdaryo, Toshkent, Navoiy va Talimarjon stansiyalarining texnik ko'rsatkichlari asos sifatida qabul qilindi.

2.3. Termodinamik hisoblash asoslari

Tutun gazidagi issiqlik potensialini baholash uchun energetik balans tenglamasi tuzib chiqildi:

$$Q_{tg} = m_{tg} * c_p * (T_{kir} - T_{chiq}) + m_b * r ; \quad (1)$$

bu yerda: Q_{tg} – tutun gazidan ajraladigan issiqlik quvvati (kVt); m_{tg} – tutun gazining massaviy sarfi (kg/s); c_p – issiqlik sigimi (kJ/(kg*K)); T_{kir} va T_{chiq} – kirish va chiqish haroratlari (°C); m_b – bug' oqimi (kg/s); r – bug'ning solishtirma bug'lanish issiqligi (kJ/kg) [14, 21].

Eksergetik samaradorlik uchun:

$$\eta_{ex} = \frac{W_{f.q}}{[Q_{tg} * (1 - \frac{T_{t.h}}{T_{tg}})]} ; \quad (2)$$

bu yerda: $W_{f.q}$ – foydali quvvat (kVt); $T_{t.h}$ – atrof-muhit harorati (K); T_{tg} – tutun gazi harorati (K) [12,14].

3. Natijalar (Results)

3.1. Asosiy texnologiyalarning tavsifi

Ko'rib chiqilgan adabiyotlar asosida tutun gazi issiqligini utilizatsiya qilishning quyidagi asosiy usullari aniqlandi (1-rasm) [1,2,6,9]:

1. Past bosimli ekonomayzerlar (PBE). Wang va boshq. [9] ning 1000 MVt quvvatli qattiq yoqilg'ili issiqlik elektr stansiyasida o'tkazilgan tadqiqotida PBE ning yillik sof foydasi 2,6 mln. AQSh dollarini tashkil etib, kapital xarajatlar 1,5 yil ichida qoplanishi ta'kidlangan. Xu va boshq. [14] ning texnik-iqtisodiy tahlili shuni ko'rsatdiki, PBE yordamida tutun gazi harorati 5 °C ga pasaytirilsa, qozon qurilmasining samaradorlik koeffitsiyenti 1% ga ortadi.

2. Organik Renkin Tsikli (ORT). Kim va boshq. [3] laboratoriya miqyosida ORT tizimini sinab ko'rib, 140 °C li tutun gazidan 220 Vt qo'shimcha elektr quvvati ishlab chiqarishga erishdi, issiqlik samaradorligi 9,4% ni tashkil etadi. Manente va boshq. [10] ORT ni termokimyoviy sorbtion issiqlik transformatori bilan integratsiyalashtirib, bitta ORT ga nisbatan quvvat unumdorligini 12-18% ga oshirishga muvaffaq bo'ldi.

3. Absorbtsion issiqlik nasosli tizimlar (AIN/OAIN). Zhang va boshq. [1] yangi ochiq absorbtsion issiqlik nasosi (OAIN) tizimini optimizatsiya qilib, yoqilg'i sarfini 0,5-2,2% ga kamaytirdi. Li va boshq. [2] tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan nol-energiya iste'moliga ega absorbtsion issiqlik nasosli (NEAIN) tizimi yiliga 17 218 tonna shartli yoqilg'iga ekvivalent issiqlikni tejaydi va 39 451 tonna CO₂ tashlamalarini kamaytiradi. Shahzad va boshq. [17] ikki pog'onali OAIN ning gigroskopik FIK 1,64 ni tashkil etishini ko'rsatadi.

4. Issiqlik quvuri asosidagi issiqlik almashtirgich (IQIA). Kang va boshq. [16] tadqiqotida IQIA ning issiqlik uzatish zichligi qovurg'alangan quvurli issiqlik almashtirgich (QQIA) ga nisbatan hajm birligi uchun 3,24 barobar yuqori ekanligi isbotlandi. IQIA issiqlikdan foydalanish darajasini 11,0% ga oshirishi, ta'minot suvi haroratini 6,9 °C ga ko'tarishi va qozon qurilmasining FIKni taxminan 1,28% ga yaxshilashi aniqlandi [16].

5. Termoelektrik generatorlar (TEG). Qozog'iston olimlaridan iborat guruh – Kubenova va boshq. [28] – raqamli modellashtirish asosida TEG uchun uch xil qanotlar konstruksiyasini taqqosladi. "Devordan-devorgacha" qanotlar konstruksiyasi 13 590,53 Vt issiqlikdan 161 Vt elektr quvvati ishlab chiqarishda eng samarali bo'lganligi aniqlandi. Olabi va boshq. [30] TEG ning sanoat va transport sohasida chiqindi issiqlik utilizatsiyasidagi keng qo'llanish imkoniyatlarini ko'rsatdi.

6. Keramik membrana kondensatorlari. Liang va boshq. [22] ko'mir kuli asosidagi, g'ovak

o'lchami 20 nm bo'lgan quvurli keramik membranalarini sinab ko'rildi. Membrana kondensatorlari tutun gazidan ham issiqlik, ham suv bug'ini bir vaqtning o'zida regeneratsiyalash imkonini beradi [25]. Yang va boshq. [24] IAIN tizimida 14,18-38,9 t/soat va FIAIN tizimida 362 t/soat suv tiklanishini qayd etdi.

3.2. Texnologiyalarning qiyosiy tahlili

Issiqlik elektr stansiyalarida organik yoqilg'ilar yoqilishi natijasida hosil bo'ladigan tutun gazlarining issiqligidan samarali foydalanish bo'yicha ko'plab tadqiqotlar o'tkazilgan. Asosan bu tadqiqotlarda taklif qilingan texnologiyalarda talab qilinadigan parametrlarga – texnologiya samara beradigan issiqlik quvvati, erishiladigan maksimal samaradorlik, kapital xarajatlar hamda texnologiyaning o'zini-o'zi qoplash muddatlari kabilar kiritilgan. Tasnifiy belgilashlarga e'tibor qaratilmaganligi esa texnologiyalarning issiqlik elektr stansiyasidagi issiqlik tashlamalaridan ikkilamchi foydalanishga qaratilgan texnologiyalar hisoblanishi bilan izohlanadi.

Taklif etilgan zamonaviy texnologiyalarni bir-biriga qiyosiy tahlil qilish orqali samaradorlik ko'rsatkichlarini baholash va tanlash imkoniyatiga ega bo'lishimiz mumkin. Quyidagi 1-jadvalda tutun gazi issiqligini utilizatsiya qilishning asosiy texnologiyalari qiyosiy tahlili keltirilgan. Ko'rib chiqilgan adabiyotlar asosida to'plangan ma'lumotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, OAIN va AIN tizimlari eng yuqori issiqlik samaradorligini ta'minlaydi (80-95%), eng qisqa o'zini qoplash muddatini esa to'la ochiq absorbtсион issiqlik nasosi ta'minlaydi - 1,4 yilgacha [1,5,7].

1-jadval. IESlarida tutun gazlari issiqligini utilizatsiya qilish texnologiyalarining qiyosiy tahlili

Table 1. Comparative analysis of flue gas heat utilization technologies at TPP

Texnologiya turi	Issiqlik quvvati (MVt)	Samaradorlik (%)	Kapital xarajat (\$/kVt)	O'z-o'zini qoplash muddati (yil)	Manba
Past bosimli ekonomayzer (PBE)	5-25	72-85	120-180	2-4	[2, 9, 14]
Organik Renkin Tsikli (ORT)	2-15	8-12	800-1500	5-8	[3, 10, 13]
Absorbtsion issiqlik nasosi (AIN)	10-50	80-95	200-400	1.4-3	[5, 7, 11]
Issiqlik quvuri iss. al-mashtirgich (IQIA)	3-18	70-83	300-600	3-5	[16, 20]
Termoelektrik generator (TEG)	0,5-5	3-7	1000-3000	7-12	[28, 30]
Keramik membrana kondensatori	2-8	60-75	400-700	3-6	[22, 25]
To'la ochiq absorbtсион iss. nasosi (OAIN)	15-65	85-95	180-350	1,4-2,5	[1, 5, 17]

3.3. Tutun gazi issiqligini utilizatsiya qilish sxemasi

1-rasm. Issiqlik elektr stansiyasida tutun gazi issiqligini utilizatsiya qilish sxemasi

Fig 1. Scheme of flue gas heat utilization at a thermal power plant

3.4. O'zbekiston IES larida utilizatsiya potentsiali

O'zbekistondagi yirik IES larni texnik tahlil qilish natijasida (2-jadval) ularning tutun gazi harorati 100-170 °C oralig'ida ekanligini aniqlandi. Sirdaryo IES kabi 3000 MVt quvvatli stansiyada 180-250 MVt issiqlik potentsiali utilizatsiya qilinmasdan tashlab yuboriladi. Toshkent IES da modernizatsiya loyihalari doirasida Italiya va Xitoy sheriklarining ishtiroki bilan IES quvvati 990 MVt ga oshirilishi rejalashtirilgan bo'lib, bu yangi utilizatsiya imkoniyatlarini yaratadi.

2-jadval. O'zbekistondagi yirik IESlarning asosiy ko'rsatkichlari va tutun gazi issiqligini utilizatsiya qilish potentsiali

Table 2. Main indicators of large TPPs in Uzbekistan and the potential for utilization of flue gas heat

IES nomi	Quvvat (MVt)	Yoqilg'i	Tutun gazi, T (°C)	Utilizatsiya potentsiali (MVt)
Sirdaryo IES	3000	Tabiiy gaz	120-150	180-250
Toshkent IES	1860	Tabiiy gaz	130-155	110-160
Navoiy IES	2151	Tabiiy gaz	125-145	130-190
Talimarjon IES	3200	Tabiiy gaz	100-130	120-200
Angren IES	286	Ko'mir	140-170	20-35

3.5. ORT tizimida ishchi suyuqliklari tahlili

Organik Renkin Tsikli uchun ishchi jismlarni tanlash tizim samaradorligiga bevosita ta'sir qiladigan omil hisoblanadi [3,10,13]. 3-jadvalda asosiy ishchi jismlar tavsifi keltirilgan. R245fa va n-pentan qattiq yoqilg'ili IESlarda tutun gazi harorati (90-150 °C) uchun eng mos ish jismi hisoblanadi. Ekologik jihatdan R1234yf va R1234ze eng maqbul variant bo'lib, ularning global isish potentsiali (GIP) ga ta'siri minimal darajada deb qaraladi [13].

3-jadval. ORC tizimida qo'llaniladigan asosiy ish jismlarining issiqlik fizik va ekologik xususiyatlari

Table 3. Thermal physical and environmental properties of the main working fluids used in the ORC system

Ishchi suyuqligi	Qaynash harati, T (°C)	Kritik harorat, T (°C)	OPP	GIP (100 yil)	Manba
R245fa	15.1	154.0	0	1030	[13, 29]
R134a	-26.4	101.1	0	1430	[3, 13]
R1234yf	-29.4	94.7	0	4	[13, 10]
R1234ze	-19.0	109.4	0	6	[13]
n-Pentan	36.1	196.5	0	~0	[29]

Izoh: OPP - ozon parchalash potentsiali; GIP - global isish potentsiali (CO₂ ga nisbatan, 100 yil uchun)

4. Muhokama (Discussion)

4.1. Texnologiyalar samaradorligini taqqoslash

Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatdiki, tutun gazi issiqligini utilizatsiya qilishning turli texnologiyalari har xil sharoitlar uchun turlicha afzalliklarga ega [6,8]. Yang va boshq. [24] tomonidan taklif etilgan FIAIN (flash-issiqlik almashtirgich-issiqlik nasosi) va IAIN (issiqlik almashtirgich-issiqlik nasosi) tizimlari tahlili shuni ko'rsatdiki, IAIN tizimi FIAIN tizimiga nisbatan 16,15-25,75 MVt ko'proq past haroratli issiqlik tashlamalarini rekuperatsiyalash, 2,37 yillik o'z-o'zini qoplash muddati bilan iqtisodiy ustunlikka ega. Tizimga qozon va issiqlik almashtirgich integratsiyalashuvi eksergetik samaradorlikni 40% ga oshiradi.

Tutun gazidan issiqlik va suvni bir vaqtning o'zida utilizatsiya qilish konsepsiyasi alohida ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. 600 MVt quvvatli elektr stansiyasida 16% hajmdagi suv bug'ini o'z ichiga olgan 150 °C haroratli tutun gazini qayta ishlash orqali 4-6 MVt elektr energiyasi va 50% suv olishga erishiladi [4]. Bu esa suv resurslarining tejami jihatidan, jumladan cho'llashgan mintaqalarda joylashgan O'zbekiston IES lari uchun, alohida ahamiyatga ega.

Nyakuma [8] Scopus ma'lumotlar bazasida 2010-2022-yillar davomidagi 123 ta maqolaning bibliometrik tahlilida uch asosiy ilmiy klasteri aniqladi: (1) issiqlik energiyasidan foydalanish va boshqarish; (2) integrallashgan energiya va resurs tiklash; (3) tizimli tahlil va optimizatsiya. Bugungi kunda, Xitoy olimlarining ilmiy tadqiqotlari global miqyosda yetakchi o'rinni egallasa-da, MDH va Markaziy Osiyo mamlakatlari olimlari ham bu sohada muhim hissa qo'shmoqdalar.

4.2. Iqtisodiy va ekologik samaradorlik

Li va boshq. [2] tahlilida nol energiya sarfili absorbsion issiqlik nasos (NEAIN) tizimining dastlabki investitsiya qiymati 15,21 mln. yuan yoki 26,8 mlrd so'm bo'lganda, yillik ko'mir tejilishi, taqriban 31 mlrd so'mni tashkil etadi. Yillik 67 136 tonna suv resurslarini tejash va 39 451 tonna CO₂ tashlamalarini qisqartirishga erishiladi. Yang va boshq. [24] tadqiqotida OAIN tizimi orqali ko'mir sarfini 36-49% ga

kamaytirishga erishilgan. O'zbekiston Sirdaryo IES kabi 3000 MVt quvvatli stansiyada bu ko'rsatkichlarni tatbiq etish yiliga 200-350 mln. AQSh dollariga teng iqtisodiy foyda keltirishi mumkin.

Jouhara va boshq. [6] chiqindi issiqlik tiklanish texnologiyalarining keng qamrovli sharhida shuni ko'rsatdiki, har 5 °C da qozon chiqish gazi haroratining pasayishi qozon samaradorligini 1% ga oshiradi, bu esa yoqilg'i sarfini 5-10% ga kamaytirish imkonini beradi va qaytim muddati 2 yildan kam bo'ladi. Shu asosda O'zbekistondagi barcha yirik IES larida PBE o'rnatish birgalikda yiliga 540-635 MVt issiqlik va ma'lum miqdordagi CO₂ tashlamalari tejallishga erishish imkonini beradi.

4.3. Mamlakatimizdagi strategik yo'nalishlar

O'zbekiston IES larining texnik ko'rsatkichlari (tabiiy gaz asosidagi yoqilg'i, 100-170 °C li tutun gazi harorati) hisobga olinib, quyidagi texnologiyalar eng istiqbolli deb topildi: (1) OAIN/AIN tizimlari – eng qisqa o'zini qoplash muddati (1,4-2,5 yil) va eng yuqori issiqlik samaradorligi (85-95%) bilan; (2) PBE - nisbatan past kapital xarajatlar (120-180 \$/kVt) va ishonchli ekspluatatsiya tajribasi bilan; (3) ORT - qo'shimcha elektr quvvati ishlab chiqarish uchun, ayniqsa 100-150 °C diapazonidagi tutun gazi uchun xos hisoblanadi.

Yangi turdagi texnologiyani tanlashda hal qiluvchi omil sifatida shudring nuqtasi haroratini hisobga olishga alohida e'tibor qaratiladi [10]. O'zbekiston IES larida tabiiy gaz asosiy yoqilg'i bo'lganligi sababli, kislotali kondensatsiya xavfi nisbatan past bo'lib, bu holatda tutun gazi haroratini (35-45 °C gacha) pasaytirish mumkin va issiqlikning katta qismini regeneratsiyalash imkoni tug'iladi.

5. Xulosa (Conclusion)

1. Absorbtsion issiqlik nasosin tizimlari (OAIN, AIN, NEAIN) tutun gazi issiqligini utilizatsiya qilishning eng samarali usuli bo'lib, 80-95% issiqlik regeneratsiyasini va 1,4-2,5 yillik o'zini qoplash muddatini ta'minlaydi [1,2,5,7].

2. ORT texnologiyasi tutun gazidan qo'shimcha quvvat ishlab chiqarish uchun istiqbolli hisoblanadi, texnologiya 8-12% issiqlik samaradorligi bilan 90-150 °C oralig'idagi past haroratli tutun gazi uchun ayniqsa mos keladi [3,10,13,29].

3. O'zbekistondagi yirik IES larida (Sirdaryo, Toshkent, Navoiy, Talimarjon) utilizatsiya qilinmagan tutun gazlarining issiqlik potentsiali 120-250 MWt ni tashkil etib, zamonaviy texnologiyalarni joriy etish yiliga sezilarli energiya va iqtisodiy foyda keltirishi mumkin.

4. Tutun gazidan issiqlik tashlamalari va suvni rekuperatsiyalash (ITSR) tizimlari O'zbekistondek cho'llashgan mintaqada suv tejamliligini ta'minlash nuqtai nazaridan alohida ahamiyatga ega [4].

5. Kelajakda tadqiqotlar zanjir bo'yicha issiqlikni rekuperatsiyalash, sun'iy intellekt asosidagi boshqaruv tizimlari va muqobil energiya manbalari bilan integratsiya yo'nalishlarida olib borilishi maqsadga muvofiq [8,11].

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